

CLASSIFYING LAND COVER FROM SATELLITE IMAGES USING RESIDUAL NETWORKS

B.Divya

Research Scholar, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Annamalai University

T.S. Subashini

Professor of Computer Science and Engineering, Annamalai University

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Abstract: Classifying satellite images is essential for comprehending and tracking the characteristics of the Earth's surface for uses like disaster relief and environmental evaluation. Using the PyTorch framework, this study investigates the use of Deep Convolutional Neural Networks (DCNN) for the classification of satellite data into four different land cover types water bodies, cultivated areas, forests and desert areas. The RSI-CB256 dataset was used to assess three Residual Network variants: ResNet-34, ResNet-50, and ResNet-152. The ResNet-50 model demonstrated an amazing 99% classification accuracy. In order to ascertain that the proposed model generalizes well, experiments were carried out with real time EuroSat dataset. The research has limitations, such as temporal and geographic biases in the dataset and the high computing cost of deeper networks like ResNet-152, despite these encouraging results.

Keywords: Deep Learning, Deep Convolutional Neural Network, Graphic Process Unit, Image classification, Machine Learning, Satellite imagery.

1. Introduction

High-resolution images of the Earth's surface obtained using satellite imaging techniques equip us with data for studying land cover. Applications for satellite image analysis are growing, including military, geospatial, surveillance, environmental impact assessments, and change monitoring. One crucial aspect of satellite image analysis is the automatic detection and classification of objects. The nature, size, and variety of visual characteristics of objects make it difficult to identify and categorize them in aerial photos. Satellite imagery finds immense use in land type classification where various land covers such as water areas, forests, vegetation lands, and desert regions could be identified and mapped.

Various applications such as land usage planning, agricultural planning and management, urban planning, disaster planning and others are highly dependent on accurate land cover classification which provides information needed for sustainable land management. There was a time when large research and development companies had the rights to satellite imagery. Until recently, owing to the acquisition nature of the satellite images, they were not publically available and access to satellite images was confined to a restricted research community or government organizations. But today it is readily available making it easier for researchers across various domains to carry out higher-level studies. Automated analysis of satellite images using computer vision is needed for making predictions and decisions as it is not feasible to analyze and interpret these images manually and even so may result in poor and suboptimal solutions. As such, automated methods for analyzing and interpreting satellite images have proven to give accurate results and thus can be undoubtedly used to derive meaningful insights from satellite images.

Deep learning techniques, in particular, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) ^{[1][2]}, have become powerful tools for satellite image classification. Diminishing gradient is one of the major problems encountered in training deep neural networks, especially with networks having many layers. This problem is caused by the gradient which becomes extremely small when back propagated from the outer layer to the previous layers. This causes the gradient to almost diminish not affecting the weight updations and as such the machine is not able to learn efficiently. To address this issue, residual connections are used in architectures like ResNet. Residual connections create shortcuts for gradient flow, which bypasses certain layers of the network and this mitigates the diminishing gradient problem and the training happens effectively in deep layered networks.

Researchers working on satellite images initially made use of machine learning techniques such as decision trees, and support vector machines (SVMs)^[3] for classifying the land types. Handcrafted features have traditionally been used in machine learning and these features are subsequently input into traditional machine learning classifiers. Machine learning methods for satellite image classification typically rely on features extracted manually and the classifier's performance is highly dependent on the quality, dimension and complexity of the extracted features^[5].

Today, deep learning techniques have been proven to be very efficient which has notably impacted computer vision tasks by replacing traditional handcrafted feature extraction methods with automatic feature extraction^[6]. The efficacy of this approach has been evidenced in tackling a wide array of computer vision problems. Specifically, satellite image analysis has particularly benefited from deep learning methodologies. Researchers have leveraged deep learning approaches for satellite image analysis tasks such as land cover classification, weather forecasting, shoreline detection, and more. In ^{[7][8]}, the authors put forward the proposition that employing deep learning methods for classifying high-resolution satellite images represents a notable advancement beyond conventional techniques.

The authors in ^[9] introduced an innovative lightweight data-driven model for weather forecasting, exploring temporal modelling methodologies such as long short-term memory (LSTM) and temporal convolutional networks. The work in ^[10] focused on change detection using the satellite image classification dataset-RSI-CB256, leveraging deep visual features to discern landscape alterations. CycleGAN and EfficientNet in ^[11] and spatial pyramid pooling in ^[12] were used to classify land usage using pre-trained models.

The work presented in this paper focuses on categorizing satellite images into four type's viz., water bodies, cultivated lands, forests and desert areas by utilizing three models of deep learning from Residual Network (ResNet) namely ResNet-34, ResNet-50 and ResNet-152. Residual Neural Networks (ResNet) have demonstrated impressive results in image classification challenges in recent years. They can be trained to learn image parameters and are sufficiently deep. In order to overcome the issue of vanishing gradients, which can make it difficult to train very deep neural networks, ResNet variations were tested in this study for the categorization of satellite photos. The paper is organized as follows. A short description of ResNet^[12] is given in Section 2 followed by the introduction of the proposed methodology in Section 3, Section 4 analyses the results obtained and compares the performance of the three ResNet models proposed in this study section 5 concludes the paper.

2. ResNet

ResNet, short for Residual Networks, is a class of deep neural network architecture^[13]. ResNet makes use of residual connections, also known as skip connections which allow the gradient to bypass certain layers, to address the vanishing gradient problem, which is a common issue in training very deep neural networks. With residual connections, gradients can propagate more efficiently through the network, enabling the training of significantly deeper architectures.

ResNet has achieved remarkable success in various computer vision tasks and has consistently outperformed previous state-of-the-art methods. The modular nature of ResNet also facilitates transfer learning, which facilitates working with relatively small datasets. Although ResNet models are not novel, the understanding that emerges from their implementation on a novel dataset has the potential to significantly advance the discipline by expanding understanding of the functional mechanisms and effectiveness of ResNet variants on varied land covers. The implementation of known models such as ResNets on a novel dataset can shed light on findings that could not be possible in earlier work. This experiment can establish a more profound comprehension of the functionality of these models on varied data types and potentially reveal previously unidentified patterns or characteristics. By contrast of ResNet variants on a novel dataset, the study shows the extent to which these models can generalize on novel, real-world data. This is particularly important given the fact that models that are superior on one dataset may not equally perform on another. Moreover, this paper presents a comparative analysis of ResNet variants in regard to the new dataset, thus providing a more lucid picture of their individual strengths and limitations. Such analysis is essential in identifying the best tools for specific tasks and may inform future model development.

The architecture of ResNet typically consists of several layers of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) followed by global average pooling and a fully connected layer for classification.

3 ResNet Architecture

The classifier based on ResNet is shown in Fig. 1. The basic building block of ResNet consists of the residual block which is used to mitigate the effects of the vanishing gradient issue by adding the original input value to the

output of the two convolution layers. This forms the core idea behind ResNet, allowing gradients to flow directly through the shortcut connections during training.

Fig. 1 Block diagram of Residual Network

Bottleneck blocks are employed in deeper variants of ResNet, to reduce computational complexity. These blocks consist of three convolutional layers: a 1x1, 3x3 and another 1x1 convolution layer. The 1x1 convolutions are used to reduce the dimensionality of the input feature maps before applying the 3x3 convolution, reducing the number of parameters and computational cost. The application of skip connections in ResNets helps in overcoming the vanishing gradient problem [14]. Without the need for learning the mapping starting from input until output directly skip connections help ResNets to understand the residual functions easily.

To carry out the dimensional reduction of the feature maps to a vector global average pooling is carried out after the convolutional layers. This is followed by a fully connected and softmax layer which maps the feature vector to class probabilities.

Fig. 2 Skip connection

ResNet architectures come in various depths, from relatively shallow variants like ResNet-18 and ResNet-34 to much deeper models like ResNet-50, ResNet-101, and ResNet-152. The ResNet model variants have been pre-trained on ImageNet and other such large datasets and this enables us to tailor these pre-trained models for various tasks such as classification, object detection and segmentation.

3.1. Methodology of the proposed work

Figure 3 depicts the overall flow diagram. Using the satellite image as input, the proposed methodology divides the topography into four classifications i.e., water bodies, cultivated lands, forests and desert areas.

Fig. 3 Overall flow diagram of the proposed work

For this, three different variants of ResNet classification models viz., Resnet-34, Resnet-50 and Resnet-152 are studied and their performance is compared. The workflow involves a comprehensive data preparation phase, encompassing the collection, preprocessing, and augmentation of satellite imagery. To guarantee that the data is in an appropriate format and quality for model training, pre-processing entails changing and preparing the data. It is an essential stage in developing a Residual Neural Network (ResNet) model for classifying satellite images. Class balance, data augmentation, and image resizing are the main pre-processing procedures being carried out. Techniques for data augmentation broaden the training dataset's diversity and enhance the model's capacity for generalization. By altering the original images through rotations, translations, flips, and brightness modifications, data augmentation produces new training examples automatically. By exposing the model to a wider variety of data fluctuations, augmentation improves the model's robustness and reduces over fitting. Feature maps are then extracted, and the images are eventually classified.

Proposed Classification Models

The applicability of the three ResNet variants namely ResNet-34, ResNet-50, and ResNet-152 for satellite image classification is experimented with in this paper. The three variants mainly differ in terms of their depth with ResNet-34, having 34 layers, and ResNet-50 and ResNet-152 with 50 and 152 layers, respectively. As the number of layers is increased, the network can produce better features that represent the image, which in turn results in good classification accuracy. The paper also compares the performance of the three variants to analyse how the increase in the number of layers impacts the classification accuracy

ResNet-34

As the name implies ResNet-34 comprises 34 layers and was one of the earlier residual networks known for its classification effectiveness. ResNet-34 was introduced in the article “Deep Residual Learning for Image Recognition”^[15] where skip connections were first employed by the authors to facilitate the training of deep CNNs. Skip connections also known as identity mappings allow the gradient to bypass certain layers, to address the vanishing gradient problem, which is a common issue in training very deep neural networks. With residual connections, gradients can propagate more efficiently through the network, enabling the training of significantly deeper architectures. Skip connections improve both the network training stability and at the same time improves the ability of the network to learn more complex features as skip connections allow the network to grow deeper and deeper without losing its effectiveness.

ResNet-50

Compared to ResNet-34, Resnet-50 is a deeper network with 50 layers and as such more complex. In addition to skip connections, Resnet-50 comprises bottleneck structures that help to reduce the computational complexity as the network gets deeper^{[16][17]}. Classification tasks that demand good performance can benefit from ResNet-50 owing to its increased depth and complexity. Most papers in the literature employing ResNet-50 for classification tasks depict very good performance on benchmark datasets such as ImageNet. As ResNet-50 strikes an effective balance between complexity and accuracy it is proposed in this work for the classification of satellite images.

ResNet-152

The deepest variant of ResNet architectures is the ResNet-152 with its 152 layers. To obtain maintain and sustain consistent efficiency and accuracy ResNet-152 employs a series of skip connections and bottleneck structures, unlike ResNet-50. This enables the network to go up to 152 layers deep without compromising efficiency. The deep structure of ResNet-152 demands more resources for training, owing to its complex nature^[18]. Compared to the other variants, ResNet-152 with its deep architecture achieves good performance on challenging datasets. ResNet-152 is thus a viable solution for applications that emphasize more on accuracy and do not bother about computational complexities.

The most computationally efficient is ResNet-34, which is appropriate for resource-constrained applications but comes at the expense of accuracy. ResNet-50 is a suitable option for situations with moderate resources since it strikes a decent mix between efficiency and performance. ResNet-152 is less suitable for resource-constrained applications because of its high computing resource requirements.

Dataset

In this work “Satellite Image Classification Dataset-RSI-CB256” from the “Kaggle” platform has been employed which is a publically available dataset^[22]. The RSI-CB benchmark dataset, which was employed in this investigation. It includes around 24,000 images 256 x 256 pixel images in six categories with 35 subclasses. To compare RSI-CB with the SAT-4, SAT-6, and UC-Merced data sets, the authors in^[23] carried out a number of studies. The results demonstrate that RSI-CB has numerous potential uses and is a better benchmark for remote sensing image classification tasks than other benchmarks in the big data era. Therefore, using a remote sensing image classification benchmark (RSI-CB) dataset based on large, scalable, and varied crowdsourcing data was suggested in this research. The dataset was first separated into training and validation data sets for the purposes of conducting the tests.

Experiments have shown that models trained on the RSI-CB256 dataset can achieve high accuracy, indicating that with proper methodologies, generalization to large and heterogeneous datasets is possible. For example, one study using the RSI-CB256 dataset achieved a remarkable accuracy of 99.64% with a scalable convolutional neural network model. Likewise, another study using MobileNet V-2 achieved accuracies of 98.40%, 95.64%, and 96.62% with the ResNet50, MobileNet V-2, and VGG-16 models, respectively. These results indicate that models trained on the RSI-CB256 dataset can efficiently identify suitable features transferable to satellite image classification.

A total of 5631 satellite images, which consist of four unique classes namely forest (1500), desert (1131), cultivated land (1500) and water (1500), mixed from sensors and Google map snapshots are available in this data set. Every image is of size of 256 × 256. However, to avoid bias, 1125 images belonging to each class were used in this study. To ensure uniformity throughout the collection, all photos were scaled to 224x224 pixels. Some sample images of the four classes from the data set used to train the proposed models are shown in Fig. 4.

Fig.4. Sample Satellite Images: Row1: Forest, Row 2: Desert, Row 3: Water bodies and Row4:Cultivated area

Results and Discussion

For carrying out the experiments the dataset was initially divided into training and validation data sets. 80% of the total 4500 satellite images covering the four different land covers was allocated for training the model and the remaining 20% was reserved for validation to ensure thorough evaluation. All images were uniformly resized to dimensions of 224x224 to maintain consistency across the dataset. The batch size of 32 was employed for optimizing computational efficiency during training iterations. Augmentation techniques such as horizontal and vertical flips, Gaussian blur, and rotation were employed to improve the model's ability to generalize well. For all three models, the Adam optimizer, learning rate of 0.001, and categorical cross-entropy loss function were utilized. In order to train deep convolutional networks, the hyper parameters (learning rate, optimizer, epochs, and batch size) were chosen based on current literature and empirical methods. Since it is an often useful starting point for the majority of deep learning tasks, including image classification using ResNet structures, a learning rate of 0.001 was used. The model overshoot the ideal answer if a high learning rate was selected, and it converged more slowly if a low learning rate was utilized. 0.001 finds a balance between stability and quick convergence. The Adam optimizer was chosen because of its adaptive learning rate mechanism, which modifies the learning rates for each parameter separately to aid in the effective training of ResNet models. By default, Adam hyper parameters such as β_1 and β_2 were configured values that produced effective categorization were 0.9 and 0.999, respectively.

The number of epochs was set to 100 in the case of ResNet-34 10 epochs in the case of ResNet-50 and 250 epochs in the case of ResNet-152.

100 epochs were chosen for ResNet-34, 10 epochs for ResNet-50 and 250 epochs were chosen for ResNet-152 in this work. The number of epochs was chosen based on typical training durations for each ResNet variant. The number of epochs was decided based on past experiments with similar architectures and datasets and empirical studies. Studies on ResNet models that were originally trained on ImageNet, and past research has shown that deeper networks like ResNet-152 require more training epochs to converge, whereas shallower models like ResNet-34 require fewer. As ResNet-152 is deep and has more parameters more number of epochs were required to learn meaningful features. In this work 250 epochs were empirically used to reach convergence for ResNet 152, whereas shallower model namely ResNet-34 converged within 100 epochs. The epochs chosen prevented overfitting and reduced training time as well.

The PyTorch ResNet-50 model prediction output of four classes such as forest, desert, cultivated and water bodies are presented in Figs. 5 to 8.

3-fold cross-validation was implemented to make the model's performance constant for varied subsets of data. Independent test set not seen during training and validation was used for realistic estimation of generalization. In order to estimate the strength of the proposed model, the model was also tested on EuroSat dataset and results show that the model generalizes well. There was no considerable loss of accuracy in training and test sets and this shows that the model generalizes between varied datasets and is not overfitted.

Fig.5 Forest Image Prediction

Fig.6 Desert Image Prediction

Fig.7 Cultivated area Image Prediction

Fig.8 Water Image Prediction

The performance of the models was evaluated using four different metrics, namely accuracy, precision, recall (sensitivity) and F1-score. These values are calculated based on confusion matrices for each class. Confusion matrix allows the visualization of the performance of a classification algorithm. It presents the summary of predictions made by the ResNet models compared to the actual values of the data set. The diagonal values represent the instances that were correctly classified, while off-diagonal elements represent miss classifications.

Forest regions are more likely to be misclassified with cultivated areas because of their comparable visual characteristics. Sometimes, especially in low-resolution photos or under specific lighting conditions, deserts and water bodies especially shallow or reflective water were mistakenly classified because of their comparable textures.

Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3 shows the performance of the three ResNet variants in categorizing the satellite images into four types of topography viz., water bodies, cultivated lands, forests and desert areas.

	Forest Area	Desert region	Cultivated Area	Water Bodies	Average Performance (%)
Accuracy	0.98	0.97	0.97	0.98	98
Precision	0.98	0.96	0.97	0.97	96.5
Recall (Sensitivity)	0.98	0.96	0.96	0.98	96.75
F1 Score	0.98	0.97	0.97	0.98	97.75

Table 1. Performance Metrics of ResNet-34

	Forest Area	Desert region	Cultivated Area	Water Bodies	Average Performance (%)
Accuracy	0.99	0.98	0.99	0.99	98.75
Precision	0.99	0.98	0.99	0.99	98.75
Recall (Sensitivity)	0.99	0.98	0.99	0.99	98.75
F1 Score	0.99	0.98	0.99	0.99	98.75

Table 2. Performance Metrics of ResNet-50

	Forest Area	Desert region	Cultivated Area	Water Bodies	Average Performance (%)
Accuracy	0.96	0.95	0.97	0.94	95.5
Precision	0.96	0.94	0.97	0.95	95.5
Recall (Sensitivity)	0.96	0.95	0.97	0.94	95.5
F1 Score	0.96	0.94	0.96	0.94	95

Table 3. Performance Metrics of ResNet-152

From Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3, it could be inferred that ResNet-50 outperformed ResNet-34 and ResNet-152 in terms of all four metrics. Resnet-50 exhibited an outstanding accuracy of 98.75 followed by Resnet-34, and Resnet-152 with 97.5% and 95.5%

The F1 score combines precision and recall to get a balanced measure of model performance. It was calculated as a harmonic mean of precision and recall as shown in the following equation.

$$F1 = 2 \times (\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall} / \text{Precision} + \text{Recall})$$

ResNet-50 topped the table in terms of F1-Score exhibiting 98.75% performance.

Category	ResNet-34 (Acc/Error)	ResNet-50 (Acc/Error)	ResNet-152 (Acc/Error)
Forest	0.98 / 2%	0.99 / 1%	0.96 / 4%
Desert	0.97 / 3%	0.98 / 2%	0.95 / 5%
Cultivated Area	0.97 / 3%	0.99 / 1%	0.97 / 3%
Water Bodies	0.98 / 2%	0.99 / 1%	0.94 / 6%
Average	0.98 / 2%	0.9875 / 1.25%	0.955 / 4.5%

Table 4.Error rate and accuracy of RSI-CB256

From the Table 4 ResNet-50 achieved the lowest error rate of 1.25%, making it the top performer. While ResNet-152 had a higher error rate of 4.5% and its worst performance was shown in the water bodies category, where the error rate reached 6%, ResNet-34 showed respectable performance with an error rate of 2%.

The graph in Fig. 9 compares the overall performance of the ResNet-34, ResNet-50 and Resnet-152 models in categorizing satellite images into various land covers namely water bodies, cultivated lands, forests, desert areas.

Fig.9. Comparison of the overall performance of the ResNet Models

This study compares the performance of ResNet-34, ResNet-50, and ResNet-152 on the RSI-CB256 dataset for satellite image classification performance. While deep learning models, such as ResNet, have been demonstrated to have improved feature extraction ability, this study did not include a comparison with traditional machine learning algorithms (e.g., SVM, Random Forest) or simple CNN models. Future studies will include these comparisons to provide a more comprehensive assessment of ResNet's advantages over traditional methods.

Category	ResNet-34 (Acc/Error)	ResNet-50 (Acc/Error)	ResNet-152 (Acc/Error)
Forest	0.97/3%	0.97/2.25%	0.94/6
Desert	0.95/5%	0.96/3.25%	0.93/6.50%
Cultivated Area	0.95/4.25%	0.97/2.25%	0.95/5.50%
Water Bodies	0.96/3.25%	0.97/2.25%	0.94/6%
Average	0.95/3.8%	0.97/2.5%	0.94 / 6%

Table 5. Error rate and accuracy of EuroSat Dataset

We also worked with EuroSat dataset to classify satellite images into four class such as forest, desert, cultivated and water bodies and the accuracy obtained is 97% as shown in Table. 5 the results validate that the model generalizes well, with no noticeable accuracy decrease between the training and test sets. This indicates that the model has the capability of generalizing from one satellite image set to another, hence making it suitable to be utilized in environmental monitoring and land cover analysis.

The performance of the proposed method is compared with similar works is show in Table 6. When compared to other models, the findings show that the suggested ResNet variants performed well.

Author reference	Algorithm used	Accuracy
Jog et al.2016 ^[2]	SVM (Support Vector Machine), KNN	83%
Pan, et al(2020) ^[6]	U-Net	90%
Qingshan Liu et al (2016) ^[11]	Multi-scale DCNNs with Spatial Pyramid Pooling (SPP-net)	91%
Mehran, et al (2023) ^[12]	Inception-ResNet	94%
Proposed work	ResNet-34,50 and 152	Average 98.75%

Table 6. Performance comparison of proposed work with similar works

However, because of the cloud cover, most satellite photographs are not very clear. The classifier's performance in this work could be significantly enhanced if the cloud cover could be eliminated from the photos before the classification stage.

As the experiments revealed that some of the images were inaccurately labeled due to clouds, the authors have worked on cloud removal using GANs as their subsequent research work. The paper deals with the elimination of the problem of cloud obstruction in satellite images by the help of Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs). Using UNet as the generator and ResNet50 as the discriminator, the proposed framework detects and deletes cloud affected areas, thus enhancing the quality of the image. The research employs the EuroSat dataset, which is augmented using Perlin noise synthetic cloud textures, for the training and testing of the models. The research has been done and published in International Conference Proceedings.

Conclusion and future discussion

In this study, three models of deep learning from Residual Network (ResNet) namely ResNet-34, ResNet-50 and ResNet-152 were experimented with, for the classification of satellite imagery into distinct land cover types, specifically focusing on water bodies, cultivated lands, forests and desert areas and their performance was compared. The workflow involves a comprehensive data preparation phase, encompassing the collection, preprocessing, and augmentation of satellite imagery. Feature maps are then extracted, and the images are eventually classified. With its moderate depth and efficient design, ResNet-50 strikes a balance between model complexity and performance, making it a good choice for satellite image classification.

Future methods could investigate sophisticated neural network architectures like EfficientNet, Vision Transformers (ViTs), and DenseNet, which are renowned for their effectiveness, scalability, and feature reuse, to improve satellite image classification. To increase accuracy and robustness, ensemble approaches like model ensembling and stacking can take advantage of the advantages of several models. Transfer learning provides a resource-efficient method of achieving high performance with low data by optimizing pre-trained models, such as those trained on ImageNet. Furthermore, limits in dataset size may be addressed by sophisticated data augmentation and synthetic data synthesis employing techniques such as GANs. These techniques aim to improve efficiency and accuracy, increasing the usefulness of satellite image classification for practical uses.

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